

Sustainable Growth of Islamic Financial Industry (IFI): Some Unresolved Issues

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ABSTRACT

After the outburst of the global financial crisis, there is a need for a new financial architecture that will offer more stable and sound system. Some proponents of Islamic finance argued that Islamic financial system could be a viable alternative to the current conventional one. Others, however, believe that it is too much to expect Islamic financial system to take a leading role on the global scale. This paper argues that Islamic financial industry (IFI) is faced with some serious issues such as lack of skilled manpower, proper regulation, supervision and transparency, lack of harmonisation and/or standardisation, and lack of Islamic benchmark, among others. These issues need to be addressed urgently in order to help the future development of IFI. Failing to deal with these issues promptly, the author argues, will not only hamper the future development of IFI but it will also lead to the convergence of IFI towards the conventional financial system.

Keywords: Islamic finance, sustainability, *Shari'ah*-compliant, standardisation, regulation, growth

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The current global financial crisis, created within the conventional financial system, brought the Islamic financial industry (IFI) into the limelight as a possible and viable alternative. Many advocates of Islamic economic system started arguing that this is the chance for the Islamic financial industry to take a central stage in the world economy. They consider IFI as a light at the

end of the tunnel. On the other hand, those more cautious and better-versed in the current status of the IFI are aware of the challenges before the IFI. For them, IFI is still too young to take a central stage or to replace the conventional economic system in the world economy. They do believe that the Islamic finance is the way forward but it is too early for this big step.

Being a niche industry, Islamic finance is faced with a long way ahead that need to be conquered before it may be elevated to the next level (Singh, 2009). Conventional economy has a history of more than 300 years and is well developed despite the shocks from the recent crisis. To expect IFI to jump over these 300 years of development is equal to a suicide and far from reality. However, some steps may be taken in order to foster and speed up the process of the development of IFI by focusing among others, on the focal points relevant for the sustainable growth of the industry.

As one author stated IFI “is in its adolescence when it comes to issues like transparency, accounting and ratings, with very different standards being used” (Robinson). For IFI to develop further and to establish its position within the mainstream global finance, it needs to make huge improvements with regard to transparency as well as to improve its credibility through harmonization of standards and practices.

Islamic finance is far from being perfect. To begin with, it is facing a number of on-going challenges that need to be addressed head on. It is the way how Muslim scholars will respond to these challenges that will determine the future of Islamic finance as stated by Karuvelil (2000, p. 155) in the following statement “The [Islamic finance] industry faces considerable challenges; its response to them will determine whether it becomes a significant alternative to the conventional system in global financial markets.” Moreover, the lack of efficient legal framework, standards and procedures, qualified manpower, and effective government support increases the risk exposures of the Islamic financial industry (Khorshid, 2009).

This paper consists of four sections including introduction. The second section briefly reviews the current status of Islamic financial industry. The next section addresses the unresolved issues within the industry that are yet to be fully addresses by both practitioners and academicians. These issues are: the of role human capital, issue of regulation, standardization or harmonization, Islamic benchmark, transparency and supervision. Final section concludes with remarks and recommendations.

2.0 CURRENT STATUS OF ISLAMIC FINANCIAL INDUSTRY

Today the Islamic finance industry is officially recognised within the global financial arena as an independent and entirely feasible financial system. The market and the demand for Islamic finance exists, it is significant and poised for further growth and expansion. However, if Islamic finance is to reach its optimal potential, a critical priority now is to ensure that the industry is firmly entrenched within a sound operating framework that forms a solid foundation for future development. Building this foundation should be accomplished before the industry moves on to a new phase characterised by innovation and expansion of industry product offerings. But the rate of new product launches and the current dynamic state of Islamic finance niche suggests that the industry may well have moved on to this next phase before actually achieving that solid foundation. This is potentially problematic in the long run when one considers the need to achieve a sustainable rate of growth in a rapidly evolving industry. (Ebrahim, 2004, p. 264)

The author of the above citation is right when he stated that there are both market and demand for Islamic finance as Islamic finance has grown into a US\$1 trillion (RM3.5trillion) industry with prospect to grow even further in the future. Moreover, there is growing awareness among Muslim population about this industry looking for business activities that are in line with *Shari'ah* teachings. Furthermore, the author is also correct when he said that Islamic finance industry rushed into the next phase without really solidifying its foundation as such, this may be detrimental to the future development of IFI. However, in my opinion, IFI is not an independent system on its own. Many authors share this view that currently IFI is only a subset to the conventional financial system. Not only that Islamic finance is a subset to the conventional system, but also it is being argued that Islamic finance is converging towards the conventional system. According to Habib Ahmad Islamic finance “is moving more and more closely to the conventional finance” and it is “mimicking most of the products of conventional finance” (Brant, 2009; Smolo, 2007, pp. 30, 44-45, 135-136).

There is no doubt that IFI needs a uniformity and standardisation as well as more regulatory, supervisory and transparency procedures that will improve its position within the global financial market. Uniformity and standardisation will promote a sound and stable Islamic financial system and make it a viable and credible component of the global financial system, while the supervisory and regulatory standards will bring about the credibility of Islamic finance (Ahmed, 2006, p. 439).

3.0 SOME UNRESOLVED ISSUES IN ISLAMIC FINANCE

3.1 Role Of Human Capital In The Development Of Islamic Finance

Many factors influence the economic development in general and the development of a financial sector in particular. Some of the factors range from social to cultural, from

economic policies to institution development, etc. The question here is: What is the role of human capital in the development of Islamic financial industry?

There are several models addressing the factors of the growth. In the traditional neoclassical growth model developed by Robert Solow and Trevor Swan in 1950s, the output of an economy is function of the capital and labour and is subject to the law of diminishing return to scale. According to this model, non-economic variables such as human capital, among others, have no function. Based on these assumptions this model implies that as the capital stock increases, growth of the economy slows down. In order to keep the economy growing there must be “incessant infusion of technological progress.” It is obvious that the technological progress is “exogenous” to this system. However, the technological process is not the main driving force for maintaining high growth rates, but rather there are other factors that are outside the realm of the neoclassical growth model (i.e. human capital).

Trying to address the above anomaly a new paradigm that became known as endogenous growth models was developed in 1980s. This model included human capital under a broader concept of capital. What this means is that due to the human capital, by adding more capital there can be increasing rather than decreasing returns to scale. It implies that both the technology and human capital are “endogenous” to this system (Hasan).

Although the above models are discussing general growth theory the same principles could be applied to the industries. Some argue that the human capital is the main factor that determines the economic growth or decline of a particular country (Garavan, Morley, Gunnigle, & Collins, 2001). Consequently the human capital is considered to be “the ultimate basis of the wealth of nations” (Hashi & Hareed).

Islamic financial industry has grown (and is still growing) rapidly over the years. However, this growth is not followed with the development of additional human capital as the industry faces a huge shortage of experienced *Shari'ah* scholars. This is one of the biggest challenges to Islamic finance industry today according to Rosly (2005, pp. 347-349). The things get more complicated with the fact that these scholars have to look into more and more sophisticated contracts that are being developed by the industry. This is the main problem according to Faisal Private Bank's CEO, Marco Rochat. Since there are “only a handful of scholars with the experience and reputation to judge the suitability of such a wide range of products” IFI is faced with a serious challenge in its quest for a share in the global financial market (Sa'Pinto, 2009).

Therefore, in order for IFI to grow further and faster, there is a need for additional a well-qualified manpower that will be well versed and equipped with necessary knowledge and skills to carry on with the mission and vision of the pioneers of IFI. Everyone has to play a role, especially the governments of the Muslim countries and their respective institutions. One good example is the step taken by Bank Negara Malaysia (Central Bank) and its establishment of The International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF). However, more needs to be done in this regard and the due attention should be given to the education of future leaders in Islamic finance by all parties involved.

3.2 Issue Of Regulation

As the current financial crisis is due to, among other things, a lack of proper regulatory policies, it is very important for Islamic financial industry to come up with a detailed framework for regulation and supervision of the financial market. This is especially true with regard to the Islamic capital market. In order for Islamic banks to avoid taking on too much risk there is a need for closer monitoring by the regulators (Sing).

The main role in the development of the regulatory framework should be carried out by various parties in the market; from governments to regulatory bodies, from financial institutions to the *Shari'ah* scholars. As stated by Tag El Din and M. Kabir Hassan there is a need for *Shari'ah* scholars to continuously monitor and overview the market in order to develop “regulatory rules based on the realities in a given market” (2007, p. 251). Both regulation and supervision are “the most vital component of a sound operating framework for Islamic finance” (Ebrahim, 2004, p. 265).

The following institutions and regulatory bodies partially addressed this issue but it is far from being solved. These institutions are:

- i. Accounting and Auditing Organization of Islamic Financial Institutions (AAIOFI)
- ii. Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB)
- iii. International Islamic Rating Agency (IIRA)
- iv. International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM)

There is no doubt that a sound and working regulations are indeed needed for IFI to not only develop further but also to gain more credibility among global masses. However, we should also make sure that the regulations are leaving enough space for the industry to breathe and function easily. Having too much regulated system is as bad as having no regulations at all.

3.3 Standardization And Harmonization Of Islamic Finance

Although there is a slight difference between the standardization and harmonization, we will not focus on this difference as such, but we will use these two terms interchangeable for the sake of the discussion. After all, Islamic financial industry is lacking both standardization as well as harmonization and it is therefore suitable to use these two terms interchangeably.

The issue of lack of standardization and/or harmonization in Islamic finance has been pointed out time and again. Yet, it is still one of the major issues faced by the Islamic financial industry. Some argue that we do not need harmonization / standardization and that the differences of opinions are the beauty of Islam and as such they are not threats to Islamic financial industry. They say that Islamic finance industry has developed tremendously over the last couple of years with over US\$1 trillion in assets. This is a fact that cannot be disputed. However, the question to ask is: What would happen and how big it would be if we have standardized it?

Others, however, acknowledge the different opinions but argue that for Islamic financial industry to prosper we need somehow standardized or harmonized rulings of basic products to help the growth of Islamic banks and financial institutions. It is rightly pointed out that different opinions on similar issued, given by different schools of thoughts, may create confusion among the general public as well as among practitioners of Islamic finance (Khir, Gupta, & Shanmagam, 2008, p. 312). Furthermore, the harmonization of *Shari'ah* standards is a prerequisite for a successful development of Islamic capital market in general and Islamic money market instruments in particular (Green, 2002). Thus, standardizing the rulings would make it easier for both companies and ordinary people to understand it better.

The operations of the Islamic banks worldwide differ to a great extent and some sort of standardization is an urgent need. Karina Robinson cited Nabeel Shoaib, global head of HSBC Amanah, the Islamic finance unit of the global bank HSBC stating that "[s]tandardization in Islamic finance is necessary to avoid fragmentation and to ultimately create a new asset class that can fully compete with conventional finance" (Robinson). Difference of opinions among *Shari'ah* scholars on what is and what is not *Shari'ah*-compliant hinders the development of the IFI. This lack of harmonisation – according to Marco Rochat – is due to the non-existence of a recognised body to oversee the Islamic financial industry. As result, “a lot of inappropriate products were sold to shariah investors” (Sa'Pinto, 2009). Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) secretary-general Rifaat Ahmed Abdel Karim, in an interview during the Reuters Global Islamic Banking Finance Summit said that the legal risk “may be one of the most significant risks

in the [Islamic financial] industry” (Sing). A lack of standardization or harmonization between the global markets (especially between the Middle East and Malaysia) makes it hard to set up a global or even regional regulatory body.

Currently, different opinions and different practices are used within a particular jurisdiction of a state or a region. Some products, for example BBA, while being acceptable in Malaysia, it is not acceptable in the Middle East region and elsewhere. We believe that the standardization of the practices and rulings would also help these practices and rulings to transcend the borders more easily.

Harmonization of the practices across the globe may bring about further growth and strength of the Islamic financial industry. This task is partially tackled by some Islamic financial institutions such as AAOIFI and IFSB, but this task is far from being done. Recent introduction of “*Shari’ah* Parameters”, introduced by the Bank Negara Malaysia, is going to help this cause. Having properly harmonized / standardized products across the globe will benefit the industry as whole and will lead to the economies of the scale. Standardization of common agreements would save time, efforts and resources, giving the Islamic finance practitioners extra space to focus on much needed area such as product development (Al-Jassar, 2002).

3.4 Islamic Benchmark

There is no doubt that Islamic finance has unique characteristics that distinguish it from other systems. However, Islamic banks today operate in the shadows of conventional financial system and their practices are indirectly affected by certain changes in conventional system (e.g. change in interest rate).

Although interest is prohibited in Islam, interest rate does affect Islamic finance and Islamic financial institutions. Islamic banks and financial institutions commonly use LIBOR as a benchmark, or in case of Malaysia KLIBOR, in order to determine their profit margin. Using interest rate is considered undesirable – according to Usmani (2002) – but it does not make the transaction invalid or *harām*, because the contract in itself does not contain interest. However, he thinks that this practice should be replaced with some kind of Islamic benchmark (pp. 48-49). The use of interest rate as a benchmark, though allowed by some *Shari’ah* scholars, should be avoided (Smolo, 2007; Vogel & Hayes, 1998, p. 139). Therefore, there is a dire need for an Islamic benchmark that will enable Islamic financial institutions to price their products based on it and to avoid any linkage to the interest.

Even though some would argue that there is no problem in using LIBOR as a benchmark, the author believes that this practice mimics the conventional finance. This way Islamic financial market is linked to the interest rate which should be avoided in the first place. Islamic financial system should be free from *ribā* (this is the claim by Islamic economists and scholars, at least in the literature), yet we are using an interest-based benchmark for our financial instruments. Responding to a question on whether we need to develop a unique Islamic benchmark, Rafe Haneef, Managing Director of Fajr Capital Plc, Kuala Lumpur, said that as long as the Islamic product fits within the mainstream product, there is no need to develop a unique Islamic benchmark.

“In my opinion, we could not create another benchmark for an Islamic product that fits within the mainstream product (Sukuk is like a bond) because the dominant benchmark (the conventional benchmark in this case) will force the new benchmark to converge. This is the law of one price in economics. However, if we change the way we structure our product (for example, if the redemption price of Sukuk is based on market price), then the pricing criteria would be different. We would have to look into the internal rate of return [IRR] in that case. If we don’t change the product, neither will the price,” he concluded (MIF).

The above citation rightly points out that the mechanism and development of the Islamic products are crucial for the development of an Islamic benchmark. Therefore, this approach of “*Shari’ah make-up*” and “decoration” in the development of Islamic products will only lead to the convergence of Islamic banks towards conventional, dominant, banking practices.

The author believes that there are briefly two steps in establishing an Islamic benchmark, namely:

- i. There is a need to develop unique products based on the *Shari’ah* and avoid the practice of copy-and-paste. As long as our products are same or similar to conventional products, there will be no true distinction between the two and therefore they will be governed by the same laws and rules of the game.
- ii. Without the implementation of the above step, there will be no Islamic benchmark that is viable in the current financial environment. However, if we manage to develop true *Shari’ah*-based products then we can simply collect the data from the market on the regular basis (daily, weekly or so) and come up with a benchmark that will be relevant to the Islamic financial market only.

Until and unless we review our practices, we will not be able to run on our own. Any attempt to develop an Islamic benchmark within the current system (having in mind that

currently IFI is a part of the conventional system) will lead to the convergence and will be subject to the law of one price as mentioned by Rafe Haneef above.

3.5 Transparency And Supervision

It is believed and many times argued that Islamic financial institutions are more transparent than their counterparts. Unfortunately, in reality, we can see that most of the conventional practices and their structures are available to the public and data regarding the conventional financial institutions are up-to-date and easily available. On the other hand, the data on Islamic financial institutions, their product structures and other related issues are difficult, in some cases impossible, to obtain not to mention that they are in most cases under the label: “*confidential*”.

This secrecy of the Islamic financial products and their structures is a double-edge sword. On one side, a bank is protecting its “intellectual property” (if any) and hides its practices and product structures from the general public. On the other hand, this hurts the bank itself, as it may benefit only the bank directly and for a short period of time. The author believes that the bank would be better off if it is to reveal its product structure to other banks and the public in general or register it under the laws governing ‘Patent Product’. By doing so, they will benefit from the increase in the market players as other banks will use that product structure (if acceptable) and increase the trade volume among the banks themselves. Furthermore, the bank will get a feedback on their product structures from the public as well as other regulatory bodies. Thus, it will lead to the improvement of the products and specialization needed for the industry to grow further.

Transparency and disclosure of a structure of product should be mandatory upon the Islamic financial institutions as to help them improve the quality of the products and their validity. This disclosure and reporting by Islamic financial institutions should comply with the highest international standards and practices for financial and non-financial reporting. Furthermore, this disclosure of the relevant information should be done accurately and timely (Khir, et al., 2008, p. 312).

The most commonly reported growth of Islamic financial industry is between 10 and 15 percent, but these reports are almost never linked to any statistical reference whatsoever. Apart from that, when the market share of the Islamic financial industry is compared to the real market data, it may be obvious that something is missing as these “reported growths” do not match the data. Thus, the information about Islamic financial industry is mostly unavailable and those available are out of date and worthless. Therefore, the transparency of Islamic financial industry is a need of the hour for the industry to

continue its growth and to establish itself in the global financial market (Ebrahim, 2004, pp. 268-269).

Non-existence of the standardized procedures and different rules and regulations applied in the process of the supervision of the Islamic financial institutions are one of the reasons why Islamic financial institutions receive lower ratings by the international rating agencies compared to the conventional counterparts (Al-Jassar, 2002, p. 176). Furthermore, we believe that the main reason for the low ratings is simply because these rating agencies treat Islamic Finance business in a same way as they treat conventional counterparty. The whole rating is based on creditor-debtor relationship as opposed to trading, equity and partnership relationship which exist in IFI. Besides, the transactions of IFI are governed by *Shari'ah* and not a man-made law.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The global financial crisis shook the international financial system around the globe and its repercussions are still being felt in the market globally. Islamic financial industry is not immune from this crisis as it has been hit as well, although to a lesser extent. This fact alone shows that Islamic financial industry is indirectly linked to the conventional counterparty as it lives under the same umbrella and is governed by the same rules of the game. In order for IFI to free itself from these conventional chains, it needs to re-establish its position within the global financial architecture as a totally separate body. This can only be done, if the current practices of IFI are thoroughly reviewed with the aim of reaching a true spirit of *Shari'ah* without any shortcuts and legal tricks.

Right now, IFI is a subset of the conventional financial system that is governed by the rules and regulations that may not be in line with the *Shari'ah*. By copying conventional mechanisms and applying the "*Shari'ah make-up*" we are not doing justice to the Islamic finance. Rather, we are marking Islamic finance subordinate to conventional financial system and thus making it less important.

In this paper we argued that without a proper manpower that is knowledgeable and skilful, without some sort of standardisation/harmonisation, and without regulations, transparency and supervision, as well as a proper product structure that will lead to the development of Islamic benchmark, the future of IFI will be at stake. In this case, IFI will slowly lose its vision and subsequently converge to the conventional counterparty.

IFI with all these issues identified above, cannot offer the full potential to the world now when it desperately needs a sustainable and stable financial system after international communities were hit by the global crisis. However, this crisis has given IFI a chance to review its existing practices and to come out of the crisis more stable and much stronger than before.

Although the issues raised in this paper are not new, they are worth mentioning once again as we are still faced with them. Lack of suitable and relevant data in support of the topic is nothing but a proof to the arguments mentioned in this paper. Further researches are needed to empirically show the importance of all of these issues for the sustainable growth of IFI. The sooner we start dealing with these issues and stop putting them aside, the sooner we will be able to achieve the objectives of the *Shari'ah* (*maqāsid al- Shari'ah*) and prosperity of IFI. If IFI fails to address the above issues promptly, then it will not only negatively affect the future development of the industry but it will also lead to the convergence of IFI towards the dominant, conventional financial system.

Another area that should be the focus of future research is the issue of defaults and legal disputes. There is still unclear picture on some (if not all) of the products offered by Islamic financial institutions. In case of Malaysia, the debate is still going on with regard to the validity of *al-Bay' Bithaman Ajil* (BBA). Although the Court of Appeal had reversed an earlier High Court decision that BBA contracts were contrary to Malaysia's Islamic banking regulations there are still many doubts about the contract. Furthermore, we have to prepare ourselves to deal with a future *sukūk* defaults that are just around the corner. The first *sukūk* defaults are already being reported and how well we manage to deal with this issue will show the real strength and potentials of the IFI (TMR).

Reference

- Ahmed, S. (2006). *Islamic Banking Finance and Insurance: A global Overview*. Kuala Lumpur: A.S. Noordeen.
- Al-Jassar, J. (2002). Islamic Finance: Successes, Prospects, and Neglected Areas *Islamic Finance: The Task Ahead - Proceedings of the Fourth Harvard University Forum on Islamic Finance* (pp. 173-176). Cambridge, Massachusetts: Center for Middle Eastern Studies, Harvard University.
- Brant, R. (2009). Is Islamic finance the answer? *BBC News (Online)*. Retrieved 06 July, 2009, from <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/business/8025410.stm>
- Ebrahim, A. I. (2004). Achieving Sustainable Growth in Islamic Finance. In S. Jaffer (Ed.), *Islamic Asset Management: Forming the Future for Shari'a-Compliant Investment Strategies*. London: Euromoney Books.
- Eldin, S. E. T., & Hassan, M. K. (2007). Islam and speculation in the stock exchange. In M. K. Hassan & M. K. Lewis (Eds.), *Handbook of Islamic Banking*. UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd.
- Garavan, T., Morley, M., Gunnigle, P., & Collins, E. (2001). Human Capital Accumulation: The Role of Human Resource Development. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 25(2).
- Green, S. K. (2002). Challenges Facing the Islamic Financial Industry *Islamic Finance: The Task Ahead - Proceedings of the Fourth Harvard University Forum on Islamic Finance* (pp. 151-154). Cambridge Massachusetts: Center for Middle Eastern Studies, Harvard University.
- Hasan, M. A. Role of Human Capital in Economic Development: Some Myths and Realities. Retrieved from http://www.unescap.org/drrpad/publication/ldec6_2174/chap1.PDF
- Hashi, A. A., & Hareed, B. A. *The Role of Human Capital Development in Economic Growth: An Islamic Analysis*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Islamic Economics and Economies of the OIC Countries 2009.
- Karuvellil, K. Z. (2000). Islamic Finance: Sustaining Success *Islamic Finance: Local Challenges, Global Opportunities - Proceedings of the Third Harvard University Forum on Islamic Finance* (pp. 155-158). Cambridge, Massachusetts: Center for Middle Eastern Studies, Harvard University.
- Khair, K., Gupta, L., & Shanmagam, B. (2008). *Longman Islamic Banking: A Practical Perspective*. Petaling Jaya: Pearson Malaysia Sdn. Bhd.
- Khorshid, A. (2009). Time to clarify opaque systems. *Islamic Banking and Finance*, 6 (5), 11-12.
- MIF, M. MIF 2007 Issuers and Investors Forum: Islamic Finance Now a Mainstream Financing Alternative. Retrieved 13 July, 2009, from http://www.mifmonthly.com/1_session2.php
- Robinson, K. Islamic finance is seeing spectacular growth. Retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com/2007/11/05/business/worldbusiness/05iht-bankcol06.3.8193171.html>
- Robinson, K. (Monday, November 5, 2007). Islamic finance is seeing spectacular growth. Retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com/2007/11/05/business/worldbusiness/05iht-bankcol06.3.8193171.html>
- Rosly, S. A. (2005). *Critical Issues on Islamic Banking and Financial Markets*. Kuala Lumpur: Dinamas.

- Sa'Pinto, M. (2009). Islamic Finance needs consistency - Faisal Pvt Bank CEO. Retrieved from <http://www.reuters.com/article/rbssBanks/idUSLF51051620090415>
- Sing, L. Y. (April 14, 2009). Islamic banks need more regulation, says industry body. *The Edge Financial Daily*, p. 9.
- Singh, H. (2009, April 30). World 'desperately' looking for sustainable financial system. *The Malaysian Resereve*, p. 14.
- Smolo, E. (2007). *A Theoretical Comparison Between Al-Bay^c Bithaman Ājil, Mushārah Mutanāqisah Partnership And Ijārah Sukūk*. International Islamic Univeristy Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur.
- TMR. (20 July 2009). First sukuk defaults set to expose soft spot. *The Malaysian Reserve*, p. 31.
- Usmani, M. T. (2002). *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*. The Hague: Kluwer Law International.
- Vogel, F. E., & Hayes, S. L. (1998). *Islamic Law & Finance: Religion, Risk & Return*. The Hague: Kluwer Law International.